

KINKING MECHANICS IN COMPOSITES UNDER COMBINED LOADING

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Introduction

- Numerical method is computationally expensive for micro-mechanics model.
- 2 D analytical micro-mechanics model for combined loading in carbon fiber composites is developed.
- As numerical method is computationally expensive for micro-mechanics model.
- Model used to predict peak compressive strength due to combined compression and torsional loading.
- Single fiber matrix unit is considered as fiber deformation representation with fiber amplitude and fiber rotation.
- Kink band mechanism with combined loading described with simultaneous increase in amplitude and fiber rotation.
- Closed form solution is obtain to get the peak load and effect of shear stress in the composites.
- Results are compared with literature [2,3] and analysis is done for combined loading.
- From present model it is observed that as shear stress increases, peak compressive stress decreases.

Micromechanical Formulation

Energy Method

$$\Pi = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^l \left\{ \left(\frac{-P^2}{E_0^2 A^2} \right) + (-2P) \left(\frac{1}{2} \omega'^2 - \frac{1}{2} \omega_0'^2 \right) + E_0^f I' (\omega' - \omega_0')^2 + A^m G_1 (\omega' - \omega_0')^2 + \frac{A^f G_1 \rho \theta}{l} (\omega' - \omega_0') \right\} dx - \frac{\eta_0}{2} \int_0^l \{ A^m G_2 (\omega' - \omega_0')^4 \} dx - T \theta$$

Results and Discussion

CONCLUSION:

- Presented new analytical micromechanical model for predicting the peak failure stress of unidirectional composites subjected to combined axial and torsional loading.
- Present analytical model can effectively predict the peak compressive load as well as the complete load-displacement and torque-rotation response under combined loading.
- The model results were validated for the carbon vinylester composite material based on data from [2].
- Present analysis indicates that remotely acting shear stress in composites degrade the compressive strength in a linear fashion.
- The composite compressive response is very nonlinear due to the presence of torsional loading and the model indicates that the nonlinearity is due to the nonlinearity of the matrix under shear loading.

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